

Impact of Rheumatic Heart Disease on Mitral Valve Pathophysiology: A Global Health Perspective

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Abstract:

Background: Rheumatic heart disease (RHD) is a leading cause of valvular morbidity in low-resource settings, with mitral valve involvement being the most prevalent. Both structural damage and secondary remodeling contribute to mitral regurgitation (MR). Understanding these mechanisms is critical for timely intervention. This study aims to assess mitral valve pathophysiology in RHD patients, focusing on structural and functional correlates of MR.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted at GMERS Medical College, Junagadh over 12 months (Dec 2023–Dec 2024). A total of 100 patients with rheumatic mitral valve disease were evaluated using clinical assessment and echocardiography. MR severity, left atrial (LA) size, annular dilatation, and atrial fibrillation (AF) were analyzed for association.

Results: Isolated mitral stenosis was seen in 44%, mixed disease in 34%, and isolated MR in 22%. MR was significantly associated with LA enlargement (68%), annular dilatation (46%), and AF (42%) ($p < 0.01$). Severe MR occurred in 7%, indicating progressive dysfunction.

Conclusion: Mitral regurgitation in RHD is strongly linked to atrial and annular remodeling, underscoring the need for early echocardiographic surveillance.

Keywords: Rheumatic Heart Disease, Mitral Valve, Mitral Regurgitation, Atrial Fibrillation, Echocardiography.

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Introduction

Rheumatic heart disease (RHD) is a major health challenge, particularly in developing countries such as India, where poverty, overcrowding, and limited healthcare access increase the incidence of untreated streptococcal pharyngitis and its sequelae. RHD is a chronic, progressive condition arising due to acute rheumatic fever that causes inflammation and fibrosis of the heart valves. The mitral valve is most commonly affected, leading to varying degrees of mitral stenosis, mitral regurgitation, or a combination of both [1]. The structural consequences include chordal shortening, commissural fusion, and leaflet thickening, all contributing to hemodynamic disturbances and clinical symptoms such as dyspnea, fatigue, and palpitations [1,2].

Recent echocardiographic studies have highlighted the dynamic nature of mitral valve dysfunction in RHD. Mitral regurgitation (MR), once considered purely structural, is now understood to have functional contributors such as left atrial (LA) dilation, mitral annular enlargement, and the

development of atrial fibrillation (AF). These mechanisms reflect an interplay between primary valvular damage and secondary cardiac remodeling. Understanding these pathophysiological processes is essential not only for improving patient outcomes through timely medical and surgical interventions but also for informing global health strategies aimed at RHD prevention and early diagnosis [3-6]. This study aims to evaluate the mitral valve changes in RHD patients over a 12-month period at a tertiary care center in western India and to analyze the associations between structural and functional parameters in the mitral valve pathology spectrum.

Methods

Study Design and Setting: This was a prospective, observational, hospital-based study carried out at the Department of Cardiology, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Junagadh, Gujarat. The study was carried out for 12 months from December 2023 to December 2024.

Study Population: A total of 100 patients with echocardiographically confirmed rheumatic mitral valve disease were included. Patients aged between 18 and 65 years, with clinical and echocardiographic diagnosis of RHD involving the mitral valve, and who provided written informed consent were part of the study. Patients with prior mitral valve surgery, significant congenital heart disease, or non-rheumatic valvular involvement were excluded.

Data Collection: Detailed demographic and clinical information was recorded at the time of enrollment, including age, gender, presenting symptoms, comorbidities, and cardiac rhythm. A complete clinical examination was performed to assess NYHA functional class, the presence of heart failure signs, and any murmurs or arrhythmias.

All participants underwent transthoracic 2D and Doppler echocardiography. The echocardiographic assessment included evaluation of mitral valve morphology, grading of mitral stenosis and regurgitation according to American Society of Echocardiography guidelines, and measurement of left atrial (LA) size and volume index. The mitral annular dimensions were assessed to identify annular dilatation, and the presence of atrial

fibrillation was confirmed by ECG and echocardiographic evidence.

Outcome Measures: The primary objective was to characterize the pathophysiological profile of mitral valve disease in RHD patients. Secondary objectives included evaluating the association between LA enlargement, annular dilatation, AF, and MR severity.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS v20. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation and compared using the Chi square test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included 100 patients, with a mean age of approximately 40 years and a female predominance (72%). A large proportion came from rural areas, highlighting the burden of RHD in underserved populations. Dyspnea was the most common presenting complaint (84%), and over one-third had advanced NYHA functional class (III or IV). Notably, atrial fibrillation was present in 38% of participants, underscoring its relevance in mitral valve pathophysiology (Table 1).

Table 1: Characteristics of Study cohort

Variable	Value (n = 100)
Mean Age (years)	39.6 ± 12.3
Female (%)	72
Rural Background (%)	81
NYHA Class III–IV (%)	36
Atrial Fibrillation (%)	38
Dyspnea (%)	84
Palpitations (%)	42
Fatigue (%)	36

Figure 1: Characteristics of the study cohort

Among the 100 patients, isolated mitral stenosis was the most commonly observed lesion (44%),

followed by mixed mitral disease (34%). Isolated MR was found in 22%. In terms of regurgitation

severity, the majority had mild MR (41%), but a notable subset (7%) had severe MR, indicating

advanced structural or functional valve damage (Table 2).

Table 2: Echocardiographic Patterns of Mitral Valve Involvement

Mitral Valve Lesion Type	Percentage (%)
Isolated Mitral Stenosis	44
Isolated Mitral Regurgitation	22
Mixed Mitral Disease	34
MR Severity	Percentage (%)
Mild	41
Moderate	17
Severe	7

Figure 2: Severity of MR.

Patients with MR (including isolated and mixed lesions) were significantly more likely to have LA enlargement and annular dilatation ($p < 0.01$). Atrial fibrillation was also strongly associated with MR presence ($p = 0.003$), suggesting the ability of atrial

and annular remodeling in the progression or worsening of regurgitation. Left ventricular systolic dysfunction was relatively uncommon and did not show significant association with MR in this cohort (Table 3).

Table 3: Structural Correlates of Mitral Regurgitation

Parameter	With MR (n = 73)	Without MR (n = 27)	p-value
LA Enlargement (%)	68	29	<0.01
Annular Dilatation (%)	46	19	<0.01
Atrial Fibrillation (%)	42	18	0.003
LV Systolic Dysfunction (%)	10	4	NS

Discussion

The findings from our study at GMERS Medical College, Junagadh, align with existing literature on rheumatic heart disease (RHD) and its impact on mitral valve pathophysiology, particularly concerning atrial fibrillation (AF), left atrial enlargement, and mitral regurgitation.

In our cohort, 38% of patients exhibited AF, a prevalence consistent with other studies. For instance, a recent study reported an increased burden of AF (36.3%) among RHD patients, emphasizing its association with LA enlargement and mitral valve lesions [7,8]. Similarly, research from Himachal Pradesh identified age, LA size, and severity of mitral stenosis as independent predisposing factors for AF in RHD patients [9]. Our study also

highlighted the prevalence of LA enlargement (68%) and annular dilatation (46%) among patients with MR. These structural changes are known contributors to the development and progression of MR. An earlier study found a significant correlation between LA size and AF in rheumatic mitral valve disease, with larger LA dimensions predisposing patients to arrhythmias. Furthermore, the combination of structural valve damage and atrial remodeling can exacerbate MR severity, leading to a vicious cycle of worsening cardiac function [10].

The interplay between MR severity, LA enlargement, and AF observed in our study aligns with the concept that functional and structural alterations in the heart are interconnected in RHD [11-13]. This relationship emphasizes the importance of early diagnosis and treatment of valvular lesions to prevent adverse remodeling and arrhythmias. Regular echocardiographic monitoring and timely intervention can mitigate the progression of these pathophysiological changes, improving patient outcomes [14,15].

Conclusion

This study highlights the complex interplay between structural and functional changes in the mitral valve apparatus among patients with RHD. A high prevalence of mitral regurgitation, left atrial enlargement, annular dilatation, and atrial fibrillation underscores the progressive nature of rheumatic mitral valve pathology. The strong association between atrial remodeling and mitral regurgitation severity emphasizes the need for early diagnosis, routine echocardiographic surveillance, and timely intervention to prevent further hemodynamic deterioration. These findings reinforce the importance of addressing RHD not only as a structural valvular disease but also as a condition with dynamic pathophysiological consequences requiring comprehensive clinical management.

References

1. Simpson MT, Kachel M, Neely RC, Erwin WC, Yasin A, Patel A, Rao DP, Pandey K, George I. Rheumatic heart disease in the developing world. *Structural Heart*. 2023 Nov 1;7(6):100219.
2. Kumar RK. Rheumatic fever and rheumatic heart disease. In Nadas' Pediatric Cardiology 2025 Jan 1 (pp. 553-566). WB Saunders.
3. Nicholson C, Hassan S, Lotto R, Kucia AM. Structural heart disease. *Cardiac Care: A Practical Guide for Nurses*. 2022 Aug 26:399-411.
4. Amogh C. A Study of Clinical and Echocardiographic Manifestations of Patients with Rheumatic Heart Disease at a Tertiary Care Hospital (Doctoral dissertation, Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences (India)).
5. Sika-Paotonu D, Beaton A, Raghu A, Steer A, Carapetis J. Acute rheumatic fever and rheumatic heart disease.
6. De-huis TJ. Critical analysis of rheumatic mitral valve surgery outcomes in central South Africa.
7. Dhungana SP, Nepal R, Ghimire R. Prevalence and factors associated with atrial fibrillation among patients with rheumatic heart disease. *Journal of Atrial Fibrillation*. 2019 Dec 31;12(4):2143.
8. Vyas P, Hasit J, Dake R, Patel I, Patel K. A Study of Spectrum of Rheumatic Heart Disease in Children at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Western India. *Journal of Clinical and Preventive Cardiology*. 2021 Apr 1;10(2):48-53.
9. Negi PC, Sondhi S, Rana V, Rathoure S, Kumar R, Kolte N, Kumar R, Rao S, Diman A, Mahajan K, Dev M, Kandoria A, Ganju N, Bhardwaj R, Merwaha R, Sharma R, Asotra S. Prevalence, risk determinants and consequences of atrial fibrillation in rheumatic heart disease: 6 years hospital based-Himachal Pradesh-Rheumatic Fever/Rheumatic Heart Disease (HP-RF/RHD) Registry. *Indian Heart J*. 2018 Dec;70 Suppl 3(Suppl 3):S68-S73.
10. Shrestha A, Shrestha R. Study of correlation of left atrial size and atrial fibrillation in rheumatic mitral valve disease. *Journal of Nepalgunj Medical College*. 2019 Dec 31;17(2):7-9.
11. Gomes NF, Silva VR, Levine RA, Esteves WA, de Castro ML, Passos LS, Dal-Bianco JP, Pantaleão AN, da Silva JL, Tan TC, Dutra WO. Progression of mitral regurgitation in rheumatic valve disease: role of left atrial remodeling. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2022 Mar 11; 9:862382.
12. Gopinath GV. Study of detection of left atrial enlargement by echocardiography and ecg correlation in cardiac and non-cardiac diseases (Doctoral dissertation, Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences (India)).
13. Cagdas M, Velibey Y, Guvenc TS, Gungor B, Guzelburc O, Calik N, Ugur M, Tekkesin AI, Gurkan K, Eren M. Evaluation of atrial electromechanical conduction delay in case of hemodynamically insignificant rheumatic heart disease: A tissue Doppler study. *Cardiology Journal*. 2015;22(6):683-90.
14. Galzerano D, Pergola V, Eltayeb A, Ludovica F, Arbili L, Tashkandi L, Di Michele S, Barchitta A, Parato MV, Di Salvo G. Echocardiography in simple congenital heart diseases: Guiding adult patient management. *Journal of Cardiovascular Echography*. 2023 Oct 1;33(4):171-82.
15. Price S, Platz E, Cullen L, Tavazzi G, Christ M, Cowie MR, Maisel AS, Masip J, Miro O,

McMurray JJ, Peacock WF. Echocardiography and lung ultrasonography for the assessment

and management of acute heart failure. *Nature Reviews Cardiology*. 2017 Jul;14(7):427-40.